

Arts and Culture in Professional Training Programmes at Beninese State Universities: From Marginalisation to Progressive Reintegration

Opêoluwa Blandine Agbaka

Université d'Abomey-Calavi, Abomey-Calavi, Benin

kaddine2@yahoo.fr

Translated by Georgina Collins

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13696815.2024.2321986>

Abstract

Artistic and cultural education has long been marginalised in the professional training provision of public universities in Benin. Individuals aspiring to artistic and cultural careers frequently travel to the West to pursue higher education, or instead they resort to self-study. In 2015, the creation of the Institut National des Arts, de l'Archéologie et de la Culture (INMAAC; National Institute for Artistic, Archaeological and Cultural Professions) made it possible to offer training more suited to the expanding needs and qualifications of arts and cultural professionals. But what has been the impact of the marginalisation of arts and culture on the professional world? What new prospects are offered by INMAAC to revitalise training? This article explores these two questions through a critical re-reading of specialist literature and oral interviews with cultural collaborators and students as well as an analysis of two collective projects carried out by INMAAC students as part of their course. The article will thus provide a basis for reflection on the need for better integration of the arts and culture within public higher education in Benin.

Introduction

In Benin's formal education system, the recreational side of arts and culture has prevailed over the technical side for a long time now. However, there were two cultural policies developed in Benin – namely, those of 1991 and 2013 – that underlined the importance of professional training for the sector's growth. Furthermore, the cultural policy and charter

of 1991 highlighted the importance of financial research into the cultural sector. And while politico-administrative authorities have protested and proclaimed the importance of arts and culture in the education system for several years (Kerlan 2007), in reality, the degree to which they are effectively implemented in education remains a problem in its own right. Ismailou Baldé, Didier N'Dah and Elise Ilboudo carried out a study on the integration of cultural heritage in higher education in Benin and Burkina Faso, showing that teaching arts and culture on university courses, for example, is somewhat marginal and does not have much of an impact on the academic community (2018).

In people's minds, culture and the arts are predominantly considered as recreational activities linked to leisure and entertainment, and this often leads to learners lacking enthusiasm towards courses in these relatively unknown and marginalised subjects. Those individuals who appear somewhat motivated to explore their interest in these academic disciplines with the aim of pursuing a related career must face opposition from parents who do not understand that artistic and cultural fields can be chosen as areas of study. According to statistics from the institute's registrar's office in 2022, around 80 per cent of students on arts courses at the Institut National des Métiers d'Art, d'Archéologie et de la Culture (INMAAC; National Institute for Artistic, Archaeological and Cultural Professions) have encountered hostility from parents for choosing to study for an arts degree.

Indifference, even hostility, towards academic study in artistic and cultural fields is deepened further due to a tendency towards perpetual hesitation (Châiné and Bruneau 1998), validated by the government's minimal investment aimed at supporting these subjects in terms of equipment, adequate infrastructure and staff qualified to run training programmes. These circumstances do little to promote the development of subjects proven to be important for the flourishing of African societies in the context of globalisation. France returning the 26 royal treasures of the Dahomey Kingdom to Benin on 10 November 2021 has sparked a general euphoria conducive to an upsurge in interest in the arts and culture among Beninese youngsters. Consequently, the development of artistic and cultural education in a Beninese context does not involve reproducing models from elsewhere, but instead offering learners areas of study that incorporate local artistic knowledge and expertise as well as offering them the potential to take a more global outlook.

This article aims to analyse the role and position of artistic and cultural education at state universities in Benin by looking at the difficulties of implementing curricula as well as academic and professional opportunities that this training can offer younger generations to encourage a revival of arts and culture in Benin. The methodology centres on a critical re-reading of specialist literature and oral interviews with students, lecturers and administrative staff, to demonstrate how artistic and cultural education remains a challenge for Beninese universities.

The first section of the article offers a broad exploration of formal arts and cultural education. Analysis then turns to Beninese state universities and the importance of INMAAC at the Université d'Abomey-Calavi (UAC; Abomey-Calavi University). Finally, the article explores the challenges of professionalisation in the arts and culture sector in Benin.

The Arts and Culture in Formal Education: A Global Issue

First, it seems pertinent to consider the definition of “éducation artistique et culturelle” (EAC; artistic and cultural education). Marie-Christine Bordeaux explains in very general terms that EAC can be seen as “the presence of the arts, of culture and the use of artistic practices in the educational sphere” (2016, 1). The French Ministry of Culture emphasises its objective to encourage children and young people to participate in artistic and cultural life through “the acquisition of knowledge, a direct connection with works of art, meeting artists and cultural professionals, an artistic and/or cultural practice”.¹ Artistic education has universal appeal, integrating artistic subjects into the education system, such as fine arts, music, theatre and dance. It embraces “all activities that aim to communicate cultural heritage to young people, and that allow them to understand and create their own artistic language” (Bamford 2006, 120).

International debates led by UNESCO on the question of EAC largely centre on its integration into school programmes, on the creation of forums for expression and for creativity, and also on the subject of education in art and education through art. The second part of this topic introduces the teaching of arts as a way of facilitating the learning process and as a factor that helps improve the results of that learning process among young people.

The UNESCO world conference held in Lisbon in 2006 defined EAC around three complementary pedagogical approaches. These are: “The study of works of art; direct contact with works of art (concerts, exhibitions, books and films); the practice of artistic activities” (UNESCO 2006). This led Bordeaux to emphasise that these pedagogical approaches offer learners the possibility of partaking, through EAC, in an aesthetic experience resulting from their contact with works of art; an artistic experience with the opportunity for them to practise their own artistic creativity; and a cultural and reflective experience through their critical gaze on the works (2016, 2).

Cultural policies are aligned and realigned around the topic of EAC, but, while positive outcomes are proven, they often struggle to be made a reality. Indeed, the main issues facing EAC lie in its semantic and structural instability, making it a concept that is continually susceptible to change and recontextualisation. As a result, it seems to be a difficult objective to achieve. In a study carried out for UNESCO in 2004–05, Anne Bamford worked in collaboration with the Australia Council for the Arts and the International Federation of Arts Councils and Culture Agencies to produce a report aimed at ascertaining the global impact of artistic teaching on the education of children and young adults. She evaluates the effects of this type of teaching on school results and highlights its various distinctive features from one country to another.

The analysis shows that our understanding of EAC diverges across the world, but common pathways can be found. Indeed, in developed countries, subjects such as music, drawing, arts and crafts, film, photography, new media and computer-aided design dominate, while in developing countries, traditions and ways of living are at the heart of learning – namely, song, folkloric dance, oral artistry, clothing design, etc. Despite this, research of a general nature has led to a hierarchisation of artistic subjects, revealing a domination of visual arts and music in cultural policy over theatre, dance and other forms of artistic expression.

The question of teaching arts and culture in a broad educational context remains an international concern with national and sometimes local nuances. Higher education, known as the top of the educational scale, does not escape the semantic and structural volatility of EAC. Francine Chaîné and Monik Bruneau (1998) underline the heterogeneity of university learners, which seems to complicate the teaching of arts and culture in higher education. In fact, at university, students within any particular academic

group come from diverse backgrounds, have had varied educational experiences and belong to different age groups. Hence, in artistic and cultural education, the multiculturalism of learners and their diversity in terms of previous education need to be considered, along with the fact that teachers may have to instruct a group that is very diverse in terms of age. Knowledge of culture also varies greatly, with some students having gained a better awareness than others at school or in extracurricular activities.

As a result, the topic of artistic teaching in higher education needs to be approached by considering the diverse profiles of learners as well as admission processes in schools and universities. At INMAAC, part of UAC in Benin, entry profiles are very eclectic, with some students having passed the general baccalaureate in literature or sciences while others have taken the technological or professional “bac” and seek to further improve their competencies. The selection of students (new undergraduates) is divided into three categories by the Ministère de l’Enseignement supérieur (Ministry of Higher Education): grant holders, the most deserving students depending on averages in the baccalaureate exams for target subjects; those who pay partial fees; and those who pay all their fees.

In recent years, it has become apparent that there is an urgent need for an accessible workforce in arts and culture, especially due to the wave of new projects related to the restitution of cultural artefacts despoiled during the colonial period. In fact, large creative projects for public and private artistic and cultural installations have revealed a significant shortage of qualified personnel able to efficiently and effectively manage such plans. Hence, over the next few years, it is essential to develop artistic and cultural training within higher education to equip Benin with a qualified and available workforce to mitigate this fundamental human resource.

Artistic and Cultural Education in Benin: An Anchor for Cultural Heritage and Operational Implementation

Analysis of the status of artistic courses in higher education cannot be carried out without considering their position in pre-school, primary and secondary education, since the education system provides a coherent scholastic pathway with an instructive framework from early years through to adolescence.

In Benin, artistic and cultural education is reduced to its simplest forms in primary teaching. Stories, songs, dancing, poetry, drawing, etc. exist as lower-ranked subjects and, in general, do not go beyond pre-school and primary-level teaching. In addition, primary school teachers must demonstrate artistic flair to young learners without being arts and culture specialists themselves. Indeed, the teaching of arts and culture requires professional expertise that primary school teachers do not necessarily have, as they are not fundamentally artists, nor have they been trained to teach arts and culture. As a way of encouraging EAC in Beninese state schools, it would be worthwhile extending an invitation to professional artists who are already equipped to teach different artistic disciplines, the effects of which would be seen in young children's increasing awareness of artistic practices.

In addition, EAC in the education system could be a forum for promoting intangible Beninese cultural heritage among young people, introducing them to knowledge, expertise and traditions. The potential of this forum remains largely underexploited. Indeed, efficient utilisation of EAC could also legitimately contribute to reducing the generation gap – widely criticised over the last few years – by inviting artists and elders to share their knowledge and understanding of Beninese society with the very youngest of pupils (Hounzandji and Agbaka 2020).

Significant marginalisation and even complete eradication of EAC in secondary state education, particularly during the democratic period beginning in 1990, have largely contributed to the invisibility of artistic practices in secondary state educational establishments in Benin. Hence, the low interest in artistic courses in higher education is simply a logical consequence of the long-term and near complete absence of EAC in secondary state education.

Conscious of this large gap in the education system, some key Beninese organisations have tried for a number of years to promote the development of EAC in youngsters' education in Benin. It was with this in mind that the Zinsou Foundation, created in 2005, organised a range of events and activities with schools, including art exhibitions and artistic programmes, with the intention of rousing interest in arts and culture among young people. The foundation offers a diverse programme for supporting artistic creativity. Launched in 2015, Le Centre (The Centre) is yet another private artistic and cultural institution established to promote visual and contemporary arts. It runs a small

museum, the Petit Musée de la Récade (Little Museum of the Récade – the “*récade*” being the Dahomey Kingdom royal staff), exhibition spaces for visual arts, creative spaces for resident artists, and a cultural outreach programme in partnership with several schools. Opening its doors in 2011, Artisttik Africa is a further private cultural institution with a focus on several different artistic disciplines, such as theatre, fine arts and film. It also offers development and educational activities in the arts to Beninese youngsters.

Moreover, since 2010, an NGO titled Benin Patrimoine (Benin Heritage) has run activities such as art-themed competitive games targeted at secondary school pupils to stimulate interest in arts and culture. Over the years, it has also organised training in traditional orality and dance for young children, with technical support from the Conservatoire des danses cérémonielles et royales du Bénin (Beninese Conservatoire for Ceremonial and Royal Dance). Another community-focused organisation along the same lines is Germes d’Afrique (Seedlings of Africa). It recently launched the Artelan project, which aims to introduce state primary school children from Parakou, Abomey-Calavi, Cotonou and Ouidah to the arts of storytelling, puppetry and theatre throughout the 2021–22 and 2022–23 school years. This programme is particularly interesting because it explores the connection between professional artists and the teaching of arts and culture in state primary schools, utilising 26 young artists who already have techniques for communicating artistic and cultural knowledge to young children. The benefits of formally involving artists in EAC within the Beninese education system could be twofold: teaching communicated by professionals, and job opportunities for experts in arts and culture.

Evidently, this anticipated revival of arts and culture within the education system cannot be achieved without adequate infrastructure to support the flourishing of artistic practice in Beninese primary schools. Beninese legislation positions the state at the centre of cultural heritage management and development plans. Hence, Article 27 of law no. 91-006 of 25 February 1991 pertaining to the cultural charter in the Republic of Benin stipulates that the Beninese state must promote the introduction of artistic and cultural disciplines in national teaching programmes. And Article 36 of the same law states that adolescence is the age group in society that is most receptive to cultural influences and the most active in economic and cultural life. Because of this, the key target group for a coherent cultural policy should be adolescents. The education system will then be

responsible for instilling a love of national cultural capital among Beninese youngsters. To move beyond good intentions to concrete actions, these duties conferred on the Beninese state can be materialised only through the formal integration of EAC in the education system, and with the associated provision of human resources, equipment and adequate artistic materials.

It should be highlighted that the “original sin”, as described by Marie-Christine Bordeaux and François Deschamps (2013), that would have removed any educative responsibility from the French Ministry of Culture since its creation, thus establishing an institutional separation between the cultural and educational sectors, is not exclusive to the French. For a long time in Benin, too, the Ministry of Culture has remained on the fringes of formal education, thus revealing a clear segregation between the ministries responsible for the three levels of education (pre-school and primary, secondary, and higher) and the Ministry of Culture. Over the last few years, the many challenges of an education system with so few artistic and cultural practices – both nationally and locally – have led to the design and launch of a project entitled “*classes culturelles*” (cultural classes). These classes aim to integrate artistic and cultural teaching by professionals into secondary-level education.

Decree no. 2018-375 of 22 August 2018 pertaining to the introduction of *classes culturelles* in the Republic of Benin officially dedicates, in Article 4, timetabled EAC on Wednesdays from 4 pm to 7 pm and on Fridays from 5 pm to 7 pm, with the option to move the timetable to set periods on Saturdays and Sundays. The Ministry of Culture is responsible for implementing this training project, working in collaboration with the Ministry for Secondary, Technical and Vocational Education. The *classes culturelles* scheme has evolved noticeably following a national recruitment drive to employ teachers in certain disciplines such as fine arts, music and dance, effectively creating trainers and appointing them to different secondary education establishments across the country. Pupils should therefore benefit from artistic and cultural learning throughout the 2022–23 school year. A framework of collaboration and dialogue between the aforementioned two institutions is now taking shape so that EAC can become a formal reality for young people in Benin.

However, it needs to be underlined that the *classes culturelles* initiative cannot thrive if higher education is not adapted to meet a probable increase in demand for training in the

arts and cultural professions over the coming years. Further, this adaptation must be carried out while considering diversification in the range of courses offered as well as logistical support for their implementation.

Artistic and Cultural Education in Beninese State Universities: From Marginalisation to Materialisation

Artistic and cultural teaching occupies a very weak position in higher education in Benin. For a long time, the teaching of arts subjects such as audiovisual media, theatre, music and graphic design has been the privilege of a few private universities and some cultural centres offering young people training that can lead to diplomas or degrees. For example, the Institut Supérieur des Métiers de l'Audiovisuel (Higher Institute for Audiovisual Professions) has been offering undergraduate degrees and professional master's degrees in film and TV production, and in skills such as sound, image, editing and postproduction. Since 2004, the École Internationale de Théâtre du Bénin (International School of Beninese Theatre) has offered higher education courses leading to a professional bachelor's degree in theatre arts and technology. Nevertheless, the importance of higher education in arts and culture requires the state's involvement as an active participant proposing educational courses that can inspire and develop the activities of private contributors with the most affordable training fees.

Unfortunately, EAC has continued to be virtually non-existent at the Université Nationale du Bénin (National University of Benin), which was created in 1970 and became the Université d'Abomey-Calavi in 2001, despite the development of the Université de Parakou (Parakou University) in the north of the country and the introduction of subject-specific universities. The appearance of the word "Arts" in the name of the former Faculté des Lettres, Arts et Sciences Humaines (FLASH; Faculty of Literature, Arts and Humanities) at UAC appears to be more of a convenient way to conform than a genuine concern regarding the integration of artistic professions in university education. The Arts Department, deprived of almost everything, including adequate infrastructure and human and financial resources, has remained a shadow of its former self for years on end. At other universities, such as Parakou, the "A" denoting Arts in the acronym FLASH does not correspond to the actual existence of an Arts Department.

Nevertheless, in 2015, the perseverance and struggle of some lecturer-researchers led to the formation of INMAAC according to decree no.

340/MESRS/CAB/DC/SGM/DRFM/DGES/R-UAC/SA, establishing the institute's creation, duties, organisation and functioning. Article 2 of this decree clarifies that INMAAC is “an institute for professionalised training, growth, research, and development support. It resumes the training formerly provided by the Université d'Abomey-Calavi in the Arts, Archaeology, Heritage, Culture and Tourism sectors.”

The creation of INMAAC therefore responds to a need for more widespread professionalisation of the arts and culture sector in Benin. Its emergence provides a more accessible alternative when it comes to educating Benin's most disadvantaged communities, thanks to grants awarded by the state and the levelling out of fees, which remain below those paid by students in other parts of the university. This more financially affordable learning prospect is an opportunity for young people aspiring to work in professions where fees for training are ordinarily two or three times higher in private centres.

INMAAC is still the only non-private organisation to offer teaching in artistic and cultural subjects at university level. It offers professional undergraduate degrees in the performing arts, fine arts, music, film and cultural administration. In the 2021–22 academic year, the institute opened its doors to 188 students across the five subject areas that make up the professional undergraduate degree. The decree for the creation of INMAAC states its training objectives in Article 4, stipulating that the institute's role is “to provide training at bachelor's, master's and doctorate levels”. It also proposes capacity building in the form of further education, in person or by distance learning, thereby contributing to the development or retraining of salaried or self-employed professionals. Also part of its remit are the design and implementation of research, training, creativity and development programmes in the arts and culture sector.

Courses are designed to give learners a solid theoretical foundation while acquiring a wide range of artistic and cultural practices. It is with this in mind that the undergraduate degree stretches over six semesters, in line with the BMD system (bachelor's–master's–doctorate – known as *système LMD* in French). The first semester and half of the second semester are designed to provide students with an interdisciplinary theoretical foundation in arts and culture, with an introduction to art history, the history of African art, the

history of Africa, that of Benin, and cultural heritage, as well as a broad introduction to the full range of different artistic professions. Specialist classes combining theory and practice begin in the second half of the second semester and last until the fifth semester, focusing primarily on the acquisition of artistic practices particular to each academic pathway. Throughout the training programme, there are lessons focusing on developing a methodology and improving writing skills and self-expression, so learners become professionals and academics capable of voicing their expertise and artistic knowledge as well as being able to conceptualise and correctly explain their approach and artistic flair. The primary focus of the sixth semester is a three-month internship in an artistic or cultural institute. And at the end of the course, students must put together an artistic or cultural assignment, thereby demonstrating their skills in designing and running a project in the arts and culture sector. At the end of all six semesters, the profiles of those graduating from each degree pathway are as follows: those students working in theatre on the Performing Arts pathway are trained to work within a range of professions such as actor, director, stage manager, set designer/scenographer, costume designer, lighting engineer, props master, theatre critic and more. On the Music pathway, target professions are musician, singer-performer, professional vocalist, professional instrumentalist (piano player, guitarist, drummer, trumpet player, percussionist, etc.), choirmaster, music teacher and more. In visual arts and on the Fine Arts pathway, graduate profiles are artist/illustrator, painter, sculptor, graphic designer, designer, artistic production workshop manager, assistant artistic director, art teacher, etc. The Film and Audiovisual Media pathway provides training for professions such as feature film and documentary director, producer, scriptwriter, production secretary, assistant director, film editor, photo manager, special effects technician, sound engineer, commercial director, music video director and TV production specialist. In arts and culture management, the Cultural Administration pathway provides training to be a cultural services manager, assistant manager in cultural administration, technical expert in the office for cultural engineering, cultural events organiser, artist manager, gallery manager, cultural coordinator, cultural product distribution manager, etc. The institute also offers professional training courses at master's level for graduates in specialist subject areas offered by the institute as well as professionals with other degrees who already work in the culture sector but would like high-level training in arts and culture.

EAC also has a positive impact on other learners (children, adolescents and young adults) who are still developing their personalities. But more than that, it helps improve their self-esteem and develop their creativity, and can even be used as a more attractive and effective tool for maintaining discipline in class (Ruppin 2010). The evaluation proposed by Jean-Marc Lauret (2007) of the effects of EAC on learners leads to the conclusion that introducing EAC in the education system allows children and adolescents to develop, among other things, skills such as an ability to take a situation and explore different possibilities, a capacity for imagination and foresight, a capability to demonstrate originality, to improve concentration during activities, to develop a new relationship with time and norms, an ability to handle stress and a capability to make one's work accessible and allow it to be evaluated by others. As a result, the implementation of artistic and cultural training in the education system at all levels can contribute enormously to the development of essential, additional competencies that can lead to success within society.

Since 2016, the Beninese government has made extensive reforms in the arts and culture sector. This planned resurgence has been marked by activities such as the launch of the Galerie Nationale (National Gallery) on 11 March 2020 and the effective process of recovering the 26 royal treasures plundered by French troops during the battle for the Dahomey Kingdom in 1892. The arrival of these objects in Benin on 10 November 2021, having been taken from Beninese land over a century ago, sparked a national euphoria exemplified by a flow of visitors to the temporary exhibition entitled "Art du Bénin d'hier à aujourd'hui" (Beninese Art from Yesterday to Today), demonstrating that Benin has great potential both for artistic creativity and also for the consumption of artistic and cultural offerings. A vast project to restructure the sector is underway, with international-standard museum construction projects and a plan to improve training courses for professionals in the arts and culture sector.

However, while waiting for these wonderful prospects to materialise over the coming years and positively impact Beninese views of the sector, the reality of the marginalisation of education in traditional artistic subjects such as fine arts, performing arts, music and dance and the rarity of high-level cultural management courses in Benin cannot be ignored. For a long time, the lack of availability of professional training in these sectors has forced some cultural learners with grants – or the financial means – to go and receive training outside Benin, primarily in the West, to meet the very

considerable challenge of a sector that is perpetually changing. Most up-and-coming contributors to the arts and culture sector have resorted to self-study, which is generally considered to promote the development of a broad range of skills. This marginalisation of artistic training in Benin's state education system has contributed towards reinforcing the notion in people's minds that training for artistic professions has no *raison d'être* in the formal education system.

In fact, as the majority of artists have not followed any specific school or university arts programme, the conclusion could be drawn that training in arts subjects is highly uncertain and not indispensable for a career in that field. Furthermore, the sorry status of Beninese artists does not motivate young people to embark on careers in the sector, for most parents do not consider artistic and cultural jobs to be worthwhile career choices and oppose the enrolment of their progeny in post-baccalaureate university subjects such as these. As head of the Department of Visual and Heritage Arts at INMAAC, I organise interview sessions with students, usually in their second academic year, to give them an opportunity to voice their reasons for enrolling at the institute, their opinions on the course, and any problems encountered during their training. Around 75 per cent of our 41 students across three years of the professional degree in fine arts (in the 2021–22 academic year) claim that their parents' response to their enrolment on the course was not encouraging and could be summarised in the following words: "You want to go to university and learn what people make and sell at the side of the road for 200, 300 francs [less than €0.50]?" This response illustrates the trivialised view people have of artistic careers, too often associated with a category of people who have very little education, struggle to make a living from their professional activities and are often sited in the margins of society.

In addition, the average person in Benin mistakes art for artisanal handicrafts and folklore, so it is difficult for most people to discern the unique character of works of art, to understand their different forms, their implications and artistic processes. Parents' reticence to encourage their offspring to study academic subjects they see as being pitiful can therefore be understood. One of the consequences of this situation is that approximately 80 per cent of students enrolled at INMAAC are grant holders, and those who sign up as fee-payers struggle to settle their tuition fees because, generally, they must pay their own educational expenses. The reality is that many parents withdraw from

paying tuition fees when their children insist on signing up. Since the institute first opened, for example, the dance and choreography course has not run every year due to a lack of students. It seems to be even more difficult for the Beninese to understand that you can go and study dance at university and then make it a career. Around 20 per cent of students abandon their training for lack of means or to go and do another course that their parents consider more suitable. The marginalisation of artistic and cultural courses in higher education results not only from the lack of interest it incites among authorities when it comes to financing infrastructure and budgeting for grants, but also from people's limited inclination towards these subjects.

Indeed, the distinctive characteristics of these courses necessitate adequate infrastructure and equipment to support the implementation of curricula. To a large extent, this specialised infrastructure is lacking. Music students, for example, must take vocal and choral lessons in rooms without soundproofing that suffer interference from ambient noise. There is no studio for fine arts students working on painting, sculpture, etc., and the film course lacks suitable space and technical equipment for training.

Moreover, it is difficult to retain the most qualified teaching staff due to unattractive salaries. Numerous issues need resolving for the institute to offer a full range of academic training in the arts and culture sector; instead, it continues to survive principally thanks to the passion and commitment of those directly involved. The familiar pattern is to do the absolute basics with whatever means available. The support and effect of partnership agreements with private organisations that have offered their space and equipment have helped, to a certain extent, with the lack of facilities and infrastructure.

The Advent of INMAAC at UAC: From Theory to Practice and the Challenge of Training Designed for the Real World

Art colleges are facing new challenges that higher education must overcome through training requirements increasingly oriented towards the needs of society and the demands of the job market. The issue of employability has been recurrent in recent years and universities are often criticised, especially in the social sciences, for not adapting training to the employment market. The sharpest criticisms denounce training for being too theoretical, and for not adapting it to developments in society (Hazelkorn 2004). Art colleges do not elude the new challenges of higher education, which, from now on, must

readjust their courses to meet the demands of society. The trend towards “all practical” courses seems to diminish the crucial importance of universities in teaching students to be citizens with a global outlook, a high analytical ability and exemplary societal engagement. According to the Conseil Supérieur de l’Éducation (Higher Education Council) in Quebec, the needs of graduates and employers are evolving rapidly, so it is important to design specialist programmes for academic training with a strong anchoring in general studies, so as not to reduce the field of training to the single matter of employability (CSE 2019). Hence, concerns regarding work readiness must not reduce universities to the simple production of graduates with specific competencies but no ability to analyse, adapt to social change, evaluate, and cast a critical eye upon society. The arts and culture sector contributes to the task of training citizens to have analytical abilities and a global outlook.

However, there is still a major concern regarding a ratio of theory to practice that allows for the development of both precise competencies and a critical mind across the different subject areas. At INMAAC, two-thirds of students are worried about the practical side of courses, to such an extent that they underestimate the importance of theory in academic education. Jean-Pierre Astolfi (1992) explains that theory is not an obstacle to practice. Instead, it helps to conceptualise and expose practice, which otherwise could be classed as somewhat esoteric. Finding a degree of balance between theory and practice in the teaching process is not always easy for either lecturers or students (Chaîné and Bruneau 2004; Bruneau 1996). Balance is gradually constructed over the course of teaching, through regular assessments for students and reviews aimed at improving the quality of education in relation to objectives.

For a long time – and, to a great extent, still today – numerous Beninese artists have struggled to conceptualise their artistic practices, despite the fact that many have proven talent and are internationally renowned. This difficulty is primarily related to a lack of training to help artists acquire the theoretical referents necessary to express themselves and explain themselves. However, it is also related to a lack of knowledge regarding the international art scene. Nationally, artistic domains still need to be structured according to professions, with clear identification of individual roles and how they contribute. The art market also needs to be formally structured.

The creation of INMAAC responded to this urgent and crucial need to train a new generation of artists with proven expertise who are also capable of developing a coherent and progressive artistic approach. These “new artists” must be capable of following and surpassing the achievements of their forebears who were successful in making a mark on the national and international arts scene with no formal training. Not only do they have the challenge of carrying the torch of their elders with dignity, but they must also bear the keys needed to carry out epistemological studies in their discipline and understand the functioning of the art world. Courses offered by the institute have been designed to provide students with a solid theoretical grounding and proven artistic experience. Budgetary shortages and the lack of appropriate equipment are what obstructs the achievement of these objectives. Nonetheless, the teaching body, supported by the institute’s administration, is trying to find solutions to these problems so the main competencies required by students can be delivered in training. This was the reason for introducing a group project to the course. This assignment is aimed at giving students the opportunity to design, develop and implement a collective project, an artistic and cultural endeavour to help them acquire essential competencies during their education at the institute. This group project is fully incorporated into the course as a unit of teaching on the INMAAC curricula, allowing for the exploration and presentation of the benefits of this type of academic activity for students at the institute and in the wider academic community at Abomey-Calavi.

This article now looks at two collective projects developed by students in the Département des Arts Visuels et du Patrimoine (Department of Visual and Heritage Arts) at INMAAC in 2021. The two projects involved students at different undergraduate levels from all subject areas offered at the institute, with the aim of pooling knowledge and competencies, thereby demonstrating the importance of professionalising the sector in Benin.

The first project, entitled “Campus Vie” (Campus Life), was designed and implemented by third-year students on the undergraduate programme in cultural administration and fine arts (2020–21). The second-year fine arts students were also involved in a creative residency. The “Campus Vie” project was developed to trace the story of student life on the Abomey-Calavi campus, from the first day they arrive at the university to the day of their graduation ceremony at the end of the course. The story of student life on campus

was told through the gaze and interpretation of fine arts students, who created works of art with that in mind (namely, paintings and digital creations; see Figures 1–6). A creative residency was organised by students in cultural administration for their counterparts in fine arts. The exhibition collated around 30 works of art divided into broad categories according to the messages conveyed. Thus, the exhibition’s scenography provided a U-shaped pathway, beginning, at the entrance to the exhibition, with works of art expressing in various ways the disorientation of the first few days of university and surprises for new undergraduates. Then there were artworks on the subject of studying conditions on campus, such as full lecture theatres, long queues at the university canteen and overcrowded student buses, but also good spots for cheap administrative services and leisure activities. End-of-course vivas were also portrayed, and the journey finished off with works of art portraying graduation ceremonies.

Some 500 visitors attended this five-day extramural exhibition on the Abomey-Calavi campus from 26 to 30 April 2021. Students in cultural administration were able to organise a concrete cultural event from initial conception through to implementation, applying strategies for mobilising financial resources. For the first time ever, they were able to collaborate closely with their peers from other subject specialisms by organising a week-long creative residency for those in fine arts, as well as a private viewing of performances from students in music and theatre.

Figures 1–6. Examples of work produced by INMAAC students for the “Campus Vie” exhibition. (Source: Photographs taken by Abdias Gbetokpanou on 26 April 2021.)

Figure 1. *1^{er} jour à l'UAC* (1st Day at UAC) by Ridwan Radji.

Figure 2. *Étonnement* (Surprise) by Ernestine Tonon.

Figure 3. *Étonnement* (Surprise) by Cassandre Goudjo.

Figure 4. *Le Savoir* (Knowledge) by Martial Adjaka.

Figure 5. *Les étoiles plein les yeux* (Dazzled by Surprise) by Floriane Djakli.

Figure 6. *Entassement royal* (A Right Royal Excess) by Emmanuel Agbo.

The second group endeavour was produced as part of a project entitled “Patrimoine en lumière” (Focus on Heritage), its main objective being to make cultural heritage more visible within higher education. Funded by the French Embassy in Benin, through the Fonds de Solidarité pour les Projets Innovants (Solidarity Fund for Innovative Projects), it allowed third-year students in the 2021–22 academic year studying on the cultural administration, fine arts, film and audiovisual media courses to set up an exhibition of paintings and photographs entitled “Patrimoine en lumière”, focusing on the cultural heritage of three of Benin’s historic cities: Abomey; Porto-Novo and Ouidah. Prior to the exhibition, 50 or so students spent three days visiting the cities to learn about their history and immerse themselves in their rich heritage. The purpose of this was to nourish their creativity. An eight-day residency was also organised for students in fine arts under the

close supervision of a fine artist teaching at the institute. Film students also attended a residency to work on the choice and development of their artistic work. These group projects were organised under the guidance of departmental heads.

In total, 30 paintings and 30 photographs were exhibited on the Abomey-Calavi campus from 19 to 29 October 2021 as part of the “Patrimoine en lumière” exhibition (Figures 7–12). The exhibition space was set up in a diptych format, with paintings displayed on one side and photographic works on the other, informing visitors about the history of these three cities through their cultural heritage. Over a thousand people came to see the students’ artworks at INMAAC during the ten-day exhibition.

Figures 7 and 8. Snapshots of the “Patrimoine en lumière” exhibition. (Source: Photographs by Gilbert Godovo, 19 October 2021.)

Figures 7 and 8. Snapshots of the “Patrimoine en lumière” exhibition. (Source: Photographs by Gilbert Godovo, 19 October 2021.)

Figures 9–12. Examples of paintings by INMAAC students for the “Patrimoine en lumière” exhibition. (Source: Photographs by Abdias Gbetokpanou, 4 May 2022.)

Figure 9. *Le courage d'un chasseur* (A Hunter's Bravery) by Emmanuel Agbo.

Figure 10. *Mythe et légende* (Myth and Legend) by Martial Adjaka.

Figure 11. *La graine de Houébadja* (The Food of Houegbadja) by Ernestine Tonon.

Figure 12. *Coexistence pacifique* (Peaceful Coexistence) by Caleb Adéléké.

There are several motives for the use of group projects as part of INMAAC student training. Essentially, they provide opportunities to:

- create a forum for collaboration so that students from different courses come together around common objectives, such as the organisation and management of artistic and cultural events;
- put into practice ideas and strategies learned during classes focused on the management of cultural projects, methods for compiling budgets, the search for funding, the coordination of art projects, etc.;
- take part in a creative residency (for fine arts students) under the guidance of professionals; and
- exhibit students' creative works to the academic community to raise awareness of arts and culture.

The group project provided a platform on which students could take centre stage before the rest of the academic community, helping them display their talent as well as new capabilities acquired during the teaching process. The aim, over time, was to promote a

certain recognition of the importance of artistic subjects at the university, and, as the institute is still relatively unknown in the academic world, it would in turn make INMAAC's training more visible. In addition, inviting parents to previews helped them realise that artistic and cultural subjects do have a place in academic education and that their children have enrolled on creative courses with attractive career opportunities.

The Importance of Training in Restructuring the Arts and Culture Sector: An Essential Foundation for Growth

Recent reforms carried out by Beninese authorities have highlighted the arts, culture and tourism as important contributing factors to development. The successful return of the Dahomey Kingdom's 26 treasures was part of a vast cultural programme that focuses on training artistic and cultural specialists to be best equipped to effectively manage the sector's envisaged innovations.

Through its artistic and cultural courses, INMAAC is well positioned, but it also requires logistical support to fully guarantee its role as a hub of high-level professional training, which is essential for the sector's growth. Most individuals working in this field have not had adequate training, and this has led to an issue regarding the sector's structure, where people take on multiple roles, which is not very productive. For example, it is common to see actors, musicians and artists try to sell their own work at the side of the road. This anomaly is a testament to the weak structure of the sector and the virtual inexistence of an ecosystem favourable to promoting the arts. The process of creation, production, distribution and exhibition of artworks is not organised enough to allow each individual to do their work correctly. The result is that visible disorder prevails in the sector, with contributors struggling to identify their duties. The progressive clarification of different occupations through adequate professional training will promote the growth of a productive ecosystem in which each qualified contributor can successfully fulfil their role, allowing for the emergence of a genuine art market in which cultural businesses can perform better.

Conclusion

By reducing arts and culture to simple fun and folklore, Beninese people cannot see their genuine importance for development. Since 1990, cultural policies have underlined the

need to integrate arts and culture into different development programmes owing to their economic impact; however, the effective implementation of such recommendations has not yet been seen. Indeed, the issue of artistic and cultural teaching in the education system in Benin is pressing. The marginalisation of EAC throughout education does not help to showcase the importance of this type of teaching when it comes to making young people in Benin into good citizens. This type of education is virtually non-existent at secondary school level and does not offer support to those young people who are inclined to choose higher-level artistic careers. The small number of passionate undergraduates who decide to enrol on artistic and cultural courses are soon discouraged by the constraints of having poor teaching equipment. The artistic and cultural curricula require a specific type of teaching space and supporting facilities so they can be implemented effectively. There are numerous challenges to overcome, and the available means are more modest than the objectives and ambitions. The efforts of INMAAC to teach these subjects to young people in Benin would be greatly strengthened if the institute were better supported financially.

Over recent years, politico-administrative authorities have actively encouraged a teaching component – supported by INMAAC – in large ongoing cultural projects. The graduation of different year groups, the strengthening of training courses with appropriate equipment and infrastructure, and the gradual diversification of subject areas within higher education all favour a burgeoning ecosystem conducive to the rise of arts and culture in Benin.

Acknowledgements

This article is part of a project that has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement no. 949378).

References

- Astolfi, Jean-Pierre. 1992. *L'École pour apprendre*. Paris: ESF Éditeur.
- Baldé, Ismailou, Didier N'Dah, and Elise Ilboudo. 2018. *Patrimoine culturel et Enseignement supérieur au Bénin et au Burkina*. Saarbrücken: Éditions Universitaires Européennes.

Bamford, Anne. 2006. "L'éducation artistique dans le monde." *Revue Internationale d'Éducation de Sèvres* 42: 119–130.

Bordeaux, Marie-Christine. 2016. "L'éducation artistique et culturelle à l'épreuve de ses modèles." *Quaderni* 92: 27–35.

Bordeaux, Marie-Christine. 2016. "Définition historique et évolution de l'éducation artistique." *Juris Arts, Etc.* 33: 19–21.

<https://fr.calameo.com/read/004648343433edf9550f0>.

Bordeaux, Marie-Christine, and François Deschamps. 2013. "Première partie. L'éducation aux arts et à la culture: d'une compétence partagée à un projet de société." In *Education artistique, l'Éternel retour?: Une ambition nationale à l'épreuve des territoires*, edited by Marie-Christine Bordeaux and François Deschamps, 17–98. Toulouse: Éditions de l'Attribut.

Bruneau, Monik. 1996. *Le monitorat: une initiative étudiante d'avenir. Rapport d'étude*. Montreal: Décanat des études de premier cycle, Université du Québec à Montréal.

Carasso, Jean-Gabriel. 2013. "Éducation artistique et culturelle 'un parcours' de combattant." *L'Observatoire* 1 (42): 81–84.

Chaîné, Francine, and Bruneau, Monik. 1998. "Introduction. De la pratique artistique à la formation d'enseignants en art." *Revue des Sciences de l'Éducation* 24 (3): 475–486.

CSE. 2019. *Les réussites, les enjeux et les défis en matière de formation universitaire au Québec*. Quebec: Conseil Supérieur de l'Éducation (CSE)..

Daabaaru. 2022. "Education artistique et culturelle en milieu scolaire au Bénin: Germes de Pensées, pour éveiller la créativité chez les écoliers." <https://daabaaru.bj/education-artistique-et-culturelle-en-milieu-scolaire-au-benin-germes-de-pensees-pour-veiller-la-creativite-chez-les-ecoliers/>.

Hazelkorn, Ellen. 2004. "Les écoles d'art de demain: enjeux et possibilités." *Éditions de l'OCDE: Politiques et Gestion de l'Enseignement Supérieur* 16 (3): 153–173.

Hounzandji, Romain Dédjinnaki, and Opêoluwa Blandine Agbaka. 2020. “La pratique du conte au Bénin: vitalité d’un art et d’un patrimoine immatériel.” *RILALE: Revue Internationale de Linguistique Appliquée, de Littérature et d’Éducation* 3 (3): 175–191.

Kerlan, Alain. 2007. “L’art pour éduquer. La dimension esthétique dans le projet de formation postmoderne.” *Éducation et Sociétés* 1 (19): 83–97.

Lang, Jack, and Cathérine Tasca. 2002. *Les arts et la culture dans l’enseignement supérieur. Protocole d’Accord*. Ministère de l’Education Nationale, Ministère de la Culture et de la Communication.

Lauret, Jean-Marc. 2007. “Les effets de l’éducation artistique et culturelle peuvent-ils être évalués.” *L’Observatoire* 2 (32): 8–11.

Ruppin, Virginie. 2010. “Quels sont les effets de l’éducation artistique? Étude d’une situation paradoxale.” *Recherches en Éducation* 8. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4000/ree.4513>.

UNESCO. 2006. “Feuille de route pour l’éducation artistique.” Paris: UNESCO. https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000384200_fre.

¹ See <https://www.culture.gouv.fr/Thematiques/Education-artistique-et-culturelle>.